

Photocatalytic CO₂ Reduction: A Review of *Ab initio* Mechanism, Kinetics, and Multi-scale Modelling Simulations

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Submitted Aug 2020

Revised Nov 2020

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Abstract

Climate change has prompted scientists to search for possible ways of reducing CO₂ emissions or even capturing it from the atmosphere. Catalytic reduction of CO₂ into value-added chemicals has been put forward as a viable strategy. While thermocatalytic routes of producing CO, methanol, methane and higher hydrocarbons from CO₂ have been the focus of considerable research efforts, photocatalytic conversion is an emerging approach. Photoactivation of CO₂ has the potential as a greener process because it could be carried out at lower temperatures and pressures, decreasing the energy consumption. The recent advent of available computational power and tools has made it possible to study the reaction *in silico* for catalyst prediction and mechanism elucidation. In this review, we thus focus on *ab initio* research of photocatalytic CO₂ reduction and comparison with experiments. The most commonly used materials are variously doped TiO₂, g-C₃N₄ and perovskites, which have favourable optical properties on their own. Their efficiency is mostly governed by the band gap, charge separation and charge transfer. Their characteristics can be improved and the catalysts tailored for a specific use by doping, introduction of defects (such as oxygen vacancies or geometric effects), cocatalysts or by using Z-scheme catalysts. Most theoretical studies focus on the calculations of conduction and valence bands, band gap and adsorption energies. Some studies try to describe the reaction mechanism. Few studies go beyond the hybrid-functional DFT approach and try to explicitly model the effect of electron excitation. While a theoretical description of the excited states is possible with post-DFT methods, it has yet to be applied to the problem of CO₂ photoreduction on a larger scale. We conclude the review with an outlook on how the current state of the art can be used for improving the existing catalysts.

Keywords: Photocatalysis; CO₂; Reduction; Theoretical modelling; Multi-scale

1 Introduction

After industrialization and becoming a carbon based society, rising CO₂ emissions have become a serious environmental problem due to its implications in the climate change. The most straightforward way of tackling this problem is to reduce the emissions but this might not be enough or even possible in all instances, where the use of fossil fuels cannot be simply avoided. A more proactive approach is to capture and convert CO₂ into value-added products ¹. Unsurprisingly, the conversion of CO₂ has received significant research attention in recent years due to the many challenges faced. CO₂ is a very stable and inert compound on account of a high C=O bond energy (750 kJ mol⁻¹)², requiring high temperatures and pressures for thermocatalytic conversion. A different viable approach is to convert CO₂ using light (photocatalysis) or electricity (electrocatalysis).

The redox potential for a single electron transfer to CO₂ is -1.85 eV (vs NHE at pH = 7). This high value stems from the fact that bending a linear CO₂ molecule and injecting an electron into its orbitals is unfavourable. The redox potential is lower than the conduction band (CB) of most semiconductors.^{3,4}

However, on certain photocatalysts CO₂ can bind in a bent configuration. An electron transfer from CO₂ upon photoexcitation to form the CO₂⁻ anion is therefore an essential process, which is dependent on the geometry of the adsorbed CO₂^{5,6}. In a bent configuration, CO₂ exhibits a lower LUMO level, which in turn facilitates the electron transfer. This means that in order to more easily reduce CO₂, adsorption in a bent configuration makes it more susceptible to receiving an electron. While a thermocatalytic CO₂ reduction requires high temperatures (at least 500 K) and pressures (10 bar) ⁷, photocatalysis can take place at room temperature and ambient pressure, with (sun)light providing the required excitation energy. As a consequence, many semiconductors have been studied for their photocatalytic properties. Upon reduction, different products might form. On copper, hydrocarbons are preferred ⁸, while silver favours CO ^{9,10}. In liquid systems, HCOOH and CH₃OH are also often formed.

The most studied materials for the photoreduction of CO₂ are metal oxides, particularly: TiO₂^{11,12,13}, MgO^{14,15}, Ga₂O₃¹⁶, Bi₂MoO₆¹⁷, In₂O₃¹⁸, Ta₂O₅¹⁹. Often, these materials are further (surface-)doped with metals such as Pt, Cu, Cr, Ru, Pd, Ag, Fe, Co, Ni^{20,21,22}, which diminish the charge recombination. This happens due to the metal acting as an electron sink, effectively trapping the electrons and stabilizing charge separation, thus improving the photocatalytic properties of the material^{23,24}.

Another technique besides doping is to combine different materials to improve their properties: such as the band gap, electron densities and stability. Combined photocatalysts such as CdSe/Pt/TiO₂²⁵, CeO₂/Bi₂MoO₆²⁶, Ag/MgO/TiO₂²⁷, CeO_x-S/ZnIn₂S₄²⁸ have been extensively studied. In recent years, there has also been a growing interest in metal free catalysts. Special attention has been devoted to g-C₃N₄ due to its non-toxicity, good stability, good absorption in the visible spectrum, and a low band gap of 2.7 eV²⁹. Despite these qualities, charge recombination hinders its photocatalytic activity³⁰. There have been several solutions proposed, such as doping (for instance with S³¹, N³², Nb, Ta, N, C³³) or using cocatalysts deposited on the catalytic surface and acting as electron traps²³. Cocatalysts are usually metals, such as Pd³⁴, Au^{35,36}, Ag^{37,24}, Pt³⁸, Cu²⁰, Fe, Co, Ni²¹. Note that surface doping or using cocatalysts differs from traditional bulk doping.

A promising alternative to cocatalysts are the so called Z-scheme catalysts³⁹. It is possible to exploit a high conduction band minimum of one semiconductor and a low valence band maximum of another one. This arrangement is called the Z-scheme and can be direct (semiconductors in contact) or indirect (a medium between the semiconductors enables the electron flow). Within the indirect Z-scheme, spatial separation can prolong the lifetime of the electrons and holes⁴⁰. This avoids the problem of finding *one* material with (1) a sufficient bandgap for the CO₂ reduction, (2) a conduction band negative enough for the reduction of CO₂ to CO₂⁻ to proceed. Z-scheme catalysts help overcome large overpotentials, increasing their photocatalytic activity^{41,42}. There are many reported Z-scheme catalysts, for instance: Ag₂WO₄/g-C₃N₄⁴³, Fe₂V₄O₁₃/RGO/CdS⁴⁴, g-C₃N₄/SnS₂⁴¹, Ag₃PO₄(111)/g-C₃N₄⁴⁵, Ag₃PO₄/TiO₂⁴⁶, Al₂O₃/g-C₃N₄⁴⁷. Research mostly focuses on synthesis, characterization and experimental performance, while the theoretical modelling is scarce.

Another way of improving a material is by introducing defects. Reports on the effects of defects (such as oxygen vacancies on photocatalytic properties of material) are somewhat inconsistent. Some researchers report that vacancies act as a charge recombination centres retarding the photocatalytic activity^{48,49}, while others found an increase in the activity^{50,51}. Bulk defects act as recombination centres⁵², while defects on surfaces seem to improve photocatalytic activity as oxygen vacancies acting as electron traps⁵³. Oxygen defects on the surface enhance the photocatalytic activity^{17,18,54,55}

Thus, there are several methods for improving photocatalytic properties of a material. The general consensus is that a good photocatalytic material should encompass a good charge separation, a fast charge transfer, absorption in the visible part of the spectrum, high stability, low cost and non-toxicity^{56,57}. Finding a photocatalyst that fulfils all of the above requirements is a remarkably difficult endeavour. Although the trial-and-error approach has historically revealed several well performing catalysts, such as TiO₂, further improvements can be achieved systematically. Computer-based design of the catalyst material is expected to play a crucial role, which underscores the importance of theoretical modelling in understanding the material properties and reaction mechanism.

In this review, we focus on a theoretical *first-principles* description of CO₂ photoreduction and subsequent kinetic or multiscale modelling based on these results. In Section 2, we discuss the fundamentals of photocatalytic CO₂ reduction. In Section 3, we focus on the theoretical description of this reaction on different scales: the electronic level, kinetic simulations and macroscale modelling (joining them together is called a multi-scale approach). Then in Section 4, an overview of CO₂ adsorption on photoactive materials is presented, followed by the first-principles calculations of materials *properties* (such as band gaps and conducting bands) in Section 5. In Section 6, an overview of the proposed mechanisms is presented together with multiscale modelling endeavours. We conclude with an outlook and future prospects in the last part.

2 Fundamentals of Photocatalytic CO₂ Reduction and Doping

While photocatalysis offers an attractive alternative to high temperature and pressure thermocatalytic reactions with the possibility of operating at ambient temperature and pressure, there are still drawbacks such as low yields, poor light absorption⁵⁸, and photocorrosion⁵⁹. Low yields are attributed to high charge recombination^{60,61}, inappropriate band gaps⁶², and slow electron transfer, while poor light absorption is caused by wider band gaps and only UV light having the sufficient energy to overcome the forbidden gap⁶². The loss of photocatalytic activity *via* photocorrosion and the problem of stability is another challenge of photocatalysts⁶³.

For any chemical reaction to proceed, the Gibbs (or Helmholtz under constant volume) free energy of the products must be lower than that of the reactants. In other words, the system's free energy must decrease. There are several ways to achieve this: with temperature, reactant/product concentrations, applied electrochemical potential, incident light *etc.* The required reduction potentials (versus the standard hydrogen electrode) for CO₂ reduction are: ^{64,65}

In photocatalysis, the conduction band minimum of the material determines the energy of the photoexcited electrons and must be lower than the reduction potential for the given reaction in order for it to occur⁶⁶. Semiconductors are most suitable for this because they exhibit a measurable yet surmountable energy difference between the highest (occupied) valence band and lowest (unoccupied) conduction band, partially conducting even without photoexcitation due to the Boltzmann tail. In metals, there is no ("forbidden") gap between the valence band maxima (VBM) and conduction band minima (CBM), enabling the electrons to move freely. Insulators, on the other hand, exhibit a

prohibitively large band gap. Semiconductors (depending on the semiconductor) lie somewhere in-between. The chemical potential of electrons in a semiconductor (or any material, for that matter) is defined analogously as that of any other species. It is the change in free energy when the species (electron) are added or removed from an (infinitely large) system. A related quantity is the Fermi level (E_F), which is defined as the work required for the addition of one electron.

Upon irradiation, electrons from VBM are excited to CBM, leaving vacancies (“holes”) in the valence band. The electrons and holes that do not recombine and reach the interface can partake in a photocatalysed reaction. For a more in-depth theoretical discussion, the reader is referred to the review by Xu and Carter.⁶⁴

Conceptually, photocatalysis occurs in three steps⁶⁷ as depicted in Figure 1. In the first step, a photon is absorbed, exciting an electron from the valence band to the conduction band and leaving a hole (vacancy) in the valence band. These electron-hole pairs can either recombine in the bulk or diffuse towards the surface, which brings about the second step, consisting of charge separation and diffusion to the surface. In the third step, the electrons and holes at the interface partake in the reduction and oxidation reactions, respectively. To improve the process, it is imperative that the photocatalyst to a large extent absorb as much light as possible and prevent charge recombination upon excitation. This can be achieved by doping, codoping, deposition of cocatalysts, introducing defects (e.g. oxygen vacancies) or combining different semiconductors (e.g. Z-scheme).

Figure 1: The three step process in photocatalysis: (i) photoexcitation, (ii) charge separation and (iii) charge transfer with the corresponding oxidation/reduction reactions. Reprinted with permission from Ref. ⁶⁷.

It is crucial that the lifetime of photoexcited electrons be long enough, which is mostly governed by the electron-hole recombination rate. This lifetime can be prolonged by trapping the electrons in a state of different multiplicity (singlet/triplet), making their recombination a spin-forbidden event. During the conversion of the singlet photoexcited state to the triplet photoexcited state, energy loss should be minimal to improve quantum efficiency. Doping can help with compound semiconductors if excited electrons and holes are physically located on different atoms, minimising the exchange splitting. Transition metals with empty, full or half-full *d*-orbitals have particularly stable electron configurations and might prove beneficial in doping as they are less likely to trap electrons. ⁶⁸

A crucial characteristic of all semiconductors is the band gap. The band gap represents the energy needed to excite an electron from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB). The band gap is intimately connected to the wavelength of the incident light to which the photocatalytic material is most

responsive. However, the value of the band gap has also other consequences. For instance, according to the ultimate efficiency hypothesis, a band gap of 1.1 eV is optimal for solar cell applications⁶⁹.

In transition metal-oxide photocatalysts, the 2p orbitals of oxygen mostly contribute to the VBM⁷⁰, located approximately 3 eV above SHE. This is too large for utilizing the wavelengths present in the visible light. As this would require the VBM to be below the reduction potential of CO₂, the VBM can be increased by doping or alloying.

Semiconductors can be doped with elements that introduce excess electron or excess vacancies, resulting in *n*-type or *p*-type materials. In a *n*-type semiconductor, the dopants provide extra electrons, which subsequently introduce the majority carriers, whereas in a *p*-type semiconductor the same principle applies for holes⁷¹. Replacing an atom in a semiconductor is therefore considered a defect, which impairs the charge equilibrium. Ghuman et al.⁷² analyzed the doping effect on amorphous TiO₂. They doped TiO₂ with both *n* and *p*-type atoms (Nb and N, respectively) and showed that doping with one type of atoms is beneficial for the reduction of the band gap and the formation of mid gap states. However, these mid gap states acted as recombination centres and hindered the photocatalytic activity. Co-doping with both types of atoms appeared to improve the photocatalytic activity relative to pristine and monodoped TiO₂. This was attributed to the localized charge deep in the band gap for monodoped systems, while in the co-doped system the mid gap states were closer to VB and CB, making electrons and holes delocalized and preventing charge recombination. Ma et al. had previously arrived at similar conclusions³³ when examining the co-doping effects on anatase TiO₂. By varying the ratio of cation and anion mixing, they showed that codoping prevents recombination without affecting the CBM. Photoabsorption in the visible region was also improved. Li et al.³² also reported that doping of TiO₂ with N not only improved its photocatalytic properties but also the absorption of the visible light.

An alternative to bulk doping is surface doping (co-catalysts). Li et al.³² analysed mesoporous TiO₂ loaded with noble metals (Pt, Au, Ag) for the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to methane. The dopants played a crucial role as the reaction rates on pristine TiO₂ were negligible, while the Pt-doped catalyst

performed best, followed by Au and Ag, demonstrating that co-catalysts promote photocatalytic activity. The effect is a function of the co-catalyst concentration as too much will depress the activity. Surface doping in reasonable amounts can increase the absorption of visible light and prevent the charge recombination as these metals act as electron sinks (Figure 2)³⁷⁷³⁷⁴⁷⁵, whereas the overabundance of surface dopants can reduce the amount of the light absorbed, thus hindering the activity.

Figure 2: Photocatalysis using a cocatalyst acting as an electron sink on the surface. Reprinted with permission from Ref. ⁷⁵. Copyright (2007) American Chemical Society.

Photocatalytic activity can be further tuned by controlling the particle size. Subramanian et al.³⁵ reported that the Au nanoparticle size affected the photocatalytic reduction efficiency and improved the generation of photocurrent. Jia et al.²³ not only reported that the nanoparticle size affects the overall activity, but also the selectivity towards methane. The size of nanoparticles is crucial, as too small particles prevent the electron transfer from the semiconductor to the nanoparticle and excessively large particles act as recombination centres⁷⁶.

The crystallinity of a semiconductor also plays a role because it increases the mobility of electron-hole pairs ^{77,78}. Therefore crystalline compounds are preferred over amorphous ones, although for instance amorphous TiO₂ can be made nearly as active as the crystalline one.⁷² Amorphous TiO₂ has a larger surface area, is easier to prepare and is isotropic. In crystalline materials, not all surfaces exhibit the same photocatalytic activity ^{34,23,79}. This was elucidated by Cao et al. ³⁴ who studied Pd (111) and Pd (100) nanoparticles on the g-C₃N₄ surface. It was evident that Pd (111) was the preferred surface due to Pd (111) being a better electron sink with a better CO₂ adsorption and CH₃OH desorption, shifting the selectivity towards methanol. This difference in activity is brought about by the charge transfer dynamics and strength of adsorption interactions. Similarly Butburee et al. ⁸⁰ studied how different TiO₂ crystal facets affect CO₂ photoreduction. Investigating three surfaces with different ratios of the (001), (101) and (010) facets, they found the pristine (001) facets to perform the worst. The (010) facet exhibited a 4-fold increase in selectivity towards methane, whereas the co-exposure of the (010) and (001) facets resulted in highest yields, which had been observed before ¹². Morphology of a photocatalyst is therefore crucial. Controlling the exposed crystal facets has a significant impact not only on the activity but also on the selectivity.

Photocatalysts encompassing a higher fraction of under-coordinated surface atoms (usually facets with high Miller indices) generally exhibit better catalytic activity. However these facets are usually thermodynamically less stable than their lower-index counterparts, rendering such finetuning challenging. Nevertheless, a significant progress has been made in recent years in the synthesis of such materials, which was for instance reviewed by Kou et al. ⁸¹ and Tu et al. ⁸²

Finding an ideal photocatalyst is therefore an arduous task. Its photocatalytic activity is affected by the chosen semiconductor, where a wide range of possibilities exist, ranging from metalloids, metal oxides to non-metal semiconductors and all possible combinations thereof. Additional tuning can be made by doping, deposition of co-catalysts and Z-scheme structures. Particle size, crystallinity and even the exposed facets also play a role. Theoretical investigations, such as screening of possible (ideal) photocatalysts, allow us to rule out non-promising candidates before resorting to experiments.

3 Theoretical description

3.1 Electronic calculations

Density functional theory (DFT) is the most commonly used approach for quantum calculations due to its favourable cost/performance ratio. Hohenberg and Kohn formulated the two theorems, which underpin the DFT, in 1964⁸³. First, for each external potential there exists exactly one ground-state electron density. Second, the density with the lowest total energy is the true density. For DFT to be practically useful, the exchange-correlation functional (XC), stemming from mapping a system of interacting electrons to a system of non-interacting electrons, must be selected wisely⁸⁴.

Historically, a local density approximation (LDA)⁸⁵ or general gradient approximation (GGA)⁸⁶ was used for XC. In LDA, the exchange-correlation part of the functional depends on the electronic density at the point in space, which brought about significant drawbacks. In GGA, the exchange-correlation part included *also* the derivative of the electronic density, bringing about improved total energies⁸⁶, atomization energies⁸⁷⁸⁸ and energy barriers⁸⁹. LDA in general overbinds atoms in solids, while GGA weakens the binding, providing more accurate cohesive energies⁹⁰.

While LDA performs poorly, GGA is still useful for metallic systems. Both approaches suffer from the self-interaction error (a small amount of the interaction of an electron with itself is retained)⁹¹. An important source of incorrect electronic density predictions is the delocalization error of functionals, which tend to spread out the electron density artificially⁹². Cohen et al.⁹³ discussed this problem on H_2^+ and showed that this error manifests in the underestimation of barriers, band gaps, dissociating energies of molecular ions and charge transfer excitation energies, and overestimation of binding energies of charge transfer complexes and the response to electric fields. Sánchez et al.⁹⁴ also attribute these incorrect predictions to the localization and delocalization error. The idea of the delocalization energy is connected to the many-electron self-interaction error⁹¹. Thus, the electronic structure is

described poorly. For instance, these functionals fail to accurately predict the band gap, underestimating it in the range of 30-100 %⁹⁵. As they often overstabilize the metallic ground states, the metallicity of the system can be completely off in the most extreme cases. For instance, the antiferromagnetic configuration of NiO is an insurmountable problem for a GGA DFT approach.⁹⁶ This problem is especially pronounced in metal oxides which represent the majority of semiconductors. However, GGA functionals are still commonly used due to their computational inexpensiveness, making periodic systems of several hundred atoms tractable.

One of the simplest solutions is the introduction of the DFT+U^{97,98,99} method, also called the Hubbard model. While plain DFT (LDA, GGA) fails to properly describe the behaviour of the transition metals due to a narrow $3d$ (and higher) band leading to the Coulomb repulsion¹⁰⁰, the strong on-site Coulomb interaction is described by an additional Hubbard-like term in DFT+U. The correction is particularly important for localized d and f electrons¹⁰¹. The Hubbard model requires two on-site parameters: U (Coulomb) and J (exchange), which can be obtained from *ab initio* calculations (such as solving many-body GW: Green's function)^{102,103}, which is too expensive for large systems, or, more commonly, determined semi-empirically by fitting a particular calculated property (such as band gap, adsorption strength etc.) to the experimentally known value.

U and J parameters are determined semiempirically and have to be fine-tuned *for the quantity* we are interested in and are not transferrable between materials. Even worse, the values of U and J depend on the environment of each atom, making the method less suitable for systems with considerable spin/oxidation state changes¹⁰⁴. It is also possible to calculate the parameters consistently from first principles but that does not offer any improvement to the accuracy of the calculations. Nevertheless, DFT+U has found great success due to its computational inexpensiveness.⁹⁷

A computationally more expensive alternative to DFT+U are hybrid functionals. They combine a portion of the exact exchange from Hartree-Fock and another part from LDA or GGA. The reasoning behind this is that they strive for an error cancellation of over-delocalised DFT and under-delocalised

HF calculations. Unfortunately, this is a computationally very expensive method when used in a plane-wave periodic system (for molecular systems using atomic orbitals it is more efficient). The accuracy depends on the functional used and the mixing ratio¹⁰⁵. Nevertheless, hybrid functionals still fail at estimating the band gap for materials with very high and very low values¹⁰⁶. Hybrid functionals are, strictly speaking, not an *ab initio* approach because the percentage of HF exchange they use had been chosen arbitrarily (usually by fitting).

Among the most commonly used functionals are B3LYP, PBE0¹⁰⁷ and HSE, which give fairly good estimations of the band gap, as shown by Marques et al.¹⁰⁶ PBE0 incorporates 25 % of the global HF exchange, which is a good compromise for most materials. However, it fails to properly describe very small or very large band-gap materials. For small band-gap materials, the optimal HF exchange would have to be around 12 % and for large-band gap materials around 70 %¹⁰⁶. HSE06¹⁰⁸ also incorporates 25 % of HF mixing (short-range only, not global) and uses an error-function screened Coulomb potential. It splits it in the short-range (SR) and long-range (LR), modestly decreasing the computational time in comparison with other hybrid functionals. The SR form of the functional is evaluated with HF while the LR is treated with PBE-GGA¹⁰⁹. Vydrov et al.¹¹⁰ illustrated that the SR term is responsible for the improved thermochemical results. The Becke-3-Lee-Yang-Par (B3LYP)^{87,111} functional is often the most used hybrid functional in molecular calculations, also including 25 % global HF exchange. Although it predicts the properties of molecules very well, it fails for periodic systems as demonstrated by Paier et al.¹¹² This is due to B3LYP failing to describe the transition from localized electrons to delocalized electrons (metals). The error is normally larger than 25 %, while for the transition and noble metals it approaches 40 %. However B3LYP can still be applied to non-metallic systems, whereas it has proven to properly describe some materials with antiferromagnetic insulating ground states (e.g. NiO, MnO, CoO).^{113,114} Consequently, HSE06 and PBE0 are the most predominantly used hybrid functionals, as shown in Table 1.

A comprehensive study and comparison of the predictions of DFT+U and hybrid functionals, particularly the effect of the Hubbard term on the band gap and reaction barriers, was conducted by

Verma et al.¹⁰¹. The authors concluded that the U value has a big impact, but is required only for atoms with d (and f) orbitals. Loschen et al.¹¹⁵ compared the LDA+ U and GGA+ U approach on CeO_2 and Ce_2O_3 and further confirmed that the U value for cerium is not transferrable between different materials and some materials (Ce_2O_3) are more sensitive to this value than others (CeO_2). Although LDA in general performs much more poorly than GGA, they demonstrated that in some cases LDA+ U is better due to a fortuitous error cancellation.

It should be noted that DFT describes the ground state. Although it is often used to estimate the band gap and even the potential energy surface of excited species, these values have strictly speaking no physical justification. The excited states are more correctly described by the time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT), which can yield information on absorption spectra, as well.

TD-DFT is used to investigate systems in excited states. Upon the absorption of a photon, the system is not in a stationary state. According to Kasha's rule, only the lowest excited state of a given multiplicity are relevant for fluorescence or phosphorescence. Structural (nuclear) relaxation of the excited system to a S_1 minimum is followed by fluorescence back to the ground state S_0 or an intersystem crossing (from singlet to triplet), which exhibits phosphorescent relaxation. TD-DFT is useful to investigate the energetics of the system on the S_1 plane, including excited state barriers and conical intersections.

Other methods include GW approximation¹¹⁶, which yields good results for bandgaps, and the Bethe-Salpeter (BSE)¹¹⁷ equation for absorption spectra. These methods are often forgone due to their exceptional computational cost and because they cannot yield thermodynamic properties or structures for they do not give total energies. Thus, most research is predominantly done using DFT.

DFT can be used to study the stability of the surfaces, to predict the adsorption energies of different species on active sites, and to perform a mechanism and kinetic analysis with respective energy barriers. Most authors focus their work on experimental findings, while theoretical investigations usually focus

on adsorption, reactions thermodynamics and occasionally the identifications of transition states, band gap and overall band structure, density of states, position of conduction and valence bands, charge transfers, and ionization potentials are the most important. Very rarely are electron excitations and other photo-induced effects rigorously accounted for.

As discussed above, the accuracy of the DFT method, the elusive chemical accuracy, depends hugely on the functional used. While a true chemical accuracy seems out of reach, qualitatively reasonable results and correct trends are not, provided a suitable functional for the problem at hand used. In *ab initio* studies, the most used GGA functional has been that of Perdew, Burke and Ernzerhof¹¹⁸ (PBE) despite all the GGA-related shortcomings.

3.2 Kinetic modelling

A multiscale model aims to describe the reaction at several (at least two) size- and time-scales. On the electronic scale, quantum approaches (most commonly (TD-)DFT) are used to obtain potential energy surfaces at the ground state S_0 and excited state S_1 (adsorption energies, reaction energies and barriers, tunnelling factors etc.). Subsequently, first-principles kinetics can be extracted using a variant of the transition state theories, followed by kinetic modelling such as microkinetic modelling or kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) simulations, which can be used to obtain the kinetics of the system.

In microkinetic modelling, a set of differential equations is solved, describing the catalyst surface, gaseous phases and, if relevant, liquid phase and interfaces. A set of differential and algebraic molar balance equations is written for every species in the corresponding phase(s) and for the balance of vacant active site(s). Usually, competitive adsorption, desorption, lateral interactions, and surface transformations are included.

For photocatalytic reactions, irradiation must also be modelled. Since 1960, the radiation transport equation (RTE) has been widely used for modelling the light adsorption in photoreactors. Also, the

excitation of individual species from S_0 to S_1 and their transformations must be described. Microkinetic modelling is not computationally demanding and allows for a quick sweep over several reaction and reactor parameters. However, it lacks the capabilities to probe the catalyst surface on the atomistic level. As it deals with averages, it cannot include the effects of adsorbate relative positions, such as lateral interactions and cooperative effects.

On the other hand, kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) can be used to obtain detailed insight into the evolution of the catalyst surface. It is a stochastic numerical method to solve the master equation. It describes a system with a state vector and time. The probability that the system exists in a given state is proportional to its energy in a Boltzmann fashion. This probability is only dependent on the previous state and not on the states leading up to it. Thus, for any given state of the system, a list of permissible reaction steps and their probabilities (proportional to their rates) can be collated. A step is then randomly chosen and the time is advanced inversely proportionally to the rate of the step. At each step, the exact configuration of the surface is evaluated and the reaction rates accordingly modified as necessary (for instance taking lateral interactions explicitly into account). While kMC is much more computationally demanding than simple microkinetic models, it offers an additional level of insight and is the most commonly used statistical technique for treating spatio-temporal events due to the complexity of real systems. When lateral interactions between the adsorbates are strong, microkinetic models may suffer from inaccuracies, whereas a kMC simulation will give correct results¹¹⁹, as demonstrated by Andersen et al.

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3.3 Macro-scale simulations

On the macro-scale, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is usually employed to study the fluid flow, pressure drop, reactor shape, catalyst loading and other real-life parameters of the reaction vessel. CFD hinges upon solving the Navier-Stokes equation, which yields the velocity field, which is coupled with the reaction mechanism. Once the velocity field is calculated, other quantities of interest (temperature,

pressure) at each point in the mesh are calculated (temperature, pressure, concentrations). Linking CFD with kinetic simulations allows for a re-calculation of the reaction parameters for each point in time and space, explicitly taking the reactor type, and subsequent heat and mass transfer effects into account.

Reactions can proceed in slurry reactors, fixed bed reactors or membrane reactors. Such theoretical simulations, although possible and executed on simple thermocatalytic systems, remain to be implemented for photocatalysis. Currently, CFD-only description (no multiscale) has been performed for CO₂ photoreduction. Despite the design of photo-reactors being equally important as the quantum description of the reaction and catalyst screening, this area of research has received considerably less attention¹²¹.

4 Calculated electronic properties

Most theoretical studies investigate electronic properties, while the treatment of reaction mechanisms (*vide infra*) is much rarer. In this section, we present an overview of the theoretical studies of photoactivation of CO₂ on heterogeneous catalysts.

Ghuman et al.⁷² investigated the effects of monodoping and codoping of amorphous TiO₂ on its electronic properties. Through calculating the band gap, total density of states (DOS) and projected density of states (PDOS), the authors concluded that doping in any form reduces the band gap of the material. However, monodoping also resulted in a decrease of photocatalytic activity. PDOS (projected DOS) of N-doped aTiO₂ showed that the *p* states of N are influencing the energy band structure due to the upshift of the tail of VB maxima, while also being responsible for the intermediate energy band found 0.95 eV below CB. It was found that this mid-gap state localizes charge carriers and results in the reduction of charge migration, acting as a recombination centre¹²². A mid-gap state is also present in Nb-doped aTiO₂, lying 0.5 eV below CB with a width of 0.3 eV. These mid-gap states do not improve the photocatalytic activity because the charge localization is larger than in pristine aTiO₂, suggesting

that these mid-gap states act as recombination centres and are reducing the charge carrier mobility. To tackle this problem, the authors co-doped their *a*-TiO₂, using both Nb and N, to introduce charge compensation and delocalize photogenerated charge carriers, effectively improving photocatalytic activity. This happens because the charge compensated co-doped system shifts the acceptor states towards the VB edge, while the donor states are shifted towards the CB edge ¹²³.

Liu et al. ¹²⁴ investigated the local density of states (LDOS) of adsorbed CO₂ on Zn₂GeO₄. The authors first calculated the band structure of pristine Zn₂GeO₄ and then proceeded to incorporate defects into the catalyst studying their effects on the adsorption of CO₂. LDOS revealed a strong bonding between C and the surface O, which is attributed to a significant overlap between the atomic orbitals of C and O. They also observed an interaction between O from CO₂ and Ge, suggesting a strong interaction of CO₂ with Zn₂GeO₄. The strongest adsorption of CO₂ on the pristine (010) surface was -1.04 eV and increased to -1.28 eV on the defective surface (oxygen vacancy), while on the (001) surface introducing an oxygen vacancy increased the interaction from -1.12 eV to -2.17 eV.

Hahn et al. ¹²⁵ investigated the adsorption and activation of CO₂ on a CeO₂ surface. They compared the partial density of states (PDOS) of free CO₂ and of linear, monodentate and bidentate adsorbed geometries of CO₂. The PDOS calculation revealed that in the linear configuration of CO₂, it exhibits the same PDOS as a free CO₂ molecule, meaning that the weak interaction is purely physisorption. The most stable adsorption was in the monodentate configuration with an adsorption energy of -0.31 eV, while the bidentate configuration appears to be closer to linear adsorption with the value of -0.12 eV, suggesting physisorption. These results apply for a 1/9 ML coverage, while at higher coverages physisorption predominates due to stronger interactions between neighbouring molecules. The calculated band gap of CeO₂ (111) was 1.99 eV.

Wang et al. ¹²⁶ investigated the doping and N vacancies effects on C₃N₄ (not to be confused with g-C₃N₄). They concluded that simultaneous doping with K and B, while also incorporating N vacancies into the material, lowers the band gap of the material. In 5 % KBH-C₃N₄, the band gap was lowered to

1.74 eV from 2.74 eV in pristine C_3N_4 . TDOS and PDOS were also computed, indicating that there was a mid-gap state present in the doped C_3N_4 acting as a recombination centre. Further analysis revealed that K and B do not significantly contribute to the formation of the mid-gap state. LUMO and HOMO were also calculated and were found to be mainly constituted by the N2p and C2p orbitals respectively. The Bader analysis concluded that the K and B atoms act as electron donors with Δq values of -1.55 and -2.10, respectively, while the N atoms act as electron acceptors with a Δq value of 1.37.

Chang et al.¹²⁷ performed calculations on a theoretically feasible material, which was proposed from first principles based on the success of g- C_3N_4 , namely a new metal-free catalyst B_4C_3 . After calculating that the material is experimentally feasible, they performed further electronic calculations to predict its characteristics. The calculated band gap was 2.39 eV. The calculated band diagram and PDOS suggested a spatial separation of the photoinduced electrons and holes, which should inhibit charge recombination.

Tafreshi et al.⁴⁵ calculated the band structure and band gap for a hybrid material $Ag_3PO_4(111)/g-C_3N_4$. The hybrid exhibits lower the band gap of 2.52 eV compared to the pristine $Ag_3PO_4(111)$ and g- C_3N_4 with a band gap of 2.75 eV and 3.13 eV, respectively. PDOS and TDOS unveiled that CBM is mostly governed by the g- C_3N_4 atomic orbitals, meanwhile the VBM is dominated by the atomic orbitals of $Ag_3PO_4(111)$.

Homlamai et al.²¹ investigated the adsorption of CO_2 and the reaction mechanism on several metal (Fe, Ni, Cu, Co) g- C_3N_4 , which we discuss in the respective sections. From PDOS, the authors determined that Fe-g- C_3N_4 should in theory display the highest adsorption energies since the atomic overlap between the metal *d*-orbitals and the CO_2 *p*-orbitals was the highest. The band gap calculations were also performed and showed that incorporating metal atoms reduces the band gap significantly. The band gap values for g- C_3N_4 , Fe- C_3N_4 , Ni- C_3N_4 , Co- C_3N_4 , Cu- C_3N_4 were 2.90, 1.31, 0.79, 0.98, 0.99 eV, respectively.

Li et al.¹²⁸ studied a GaP/TiO₂ heterostructure, where an unstable GaP surface is coated with TiO₂. The authors calculated the band gap and DOS. The band gap value was reduced to 1.5 eV (relative to pristine GaP with a band gap of 2.26 eV), which was attributed to the GaP increasing VBM of the heterostructure, shown by DOS. Furthermore, it was found that the heterostructure promotes charge carrier separation due to the electrons having their lowest energy states in TiO₂, while the photoinduced hole remained in GaP.

Wang et al.³¹ took a closer look at S-doped g-C₃N₄. They found that PBE-GGA calculations significantly underestimated the band gap. The experimental value was 2.55 eV, while the calculated value was only 1.18 eV (see discussion in the previous subsection). TDOS and PDOS were also calculated, showing that the incorporation of a sulphur atom into the matrix brought an extra electron, consequently introducing spin polarization.

A different study of S doped g-C₃N₄ was performed by Wang et al.,¹²⁹ where a hybrid functional (HSE06) was used, which yielded a much better agreement with the experimental. The calculated band gap was 2.42 eV (experimental: 2.55 eV). In pristine g-C₃N₄, HOMO is mostly localized on N atoms, whereas LUMO comprises mostly of C atoms. Upon doping with S, HOMO mostly moves to N atoms, while LUMO is located on S atoms, indicating a better charge separation. The authors also calculated the band edge for both catalysts using the work function. The resulting values for CBM were -1.05 and -1.11 V for g-C₃N₄ and S-doped g-C₃N₄, respectively, which is above the CO₂/CH₃OH potential. The VBM values were calculated to be 1.75 and 1.31 V for g-C₃N₄ and S-doped g-C₃N₄, respectively, which is below the CO₂/CH₃OH potential. This indicates that both are capable of reducing CO₂ to methanol, with the S-doped g-C₃N₄ having a slightly higher (for 0.06 V) located CBM than g-C₃N₄.

As discussed in the previous section and seen here (see also Table 1), hybrid functionals are necessary for a proper electronic structure description. The general trend is that doping reduces the band gap, which is favourable for visible light absorption⁷²¹²⁶. However, doping might not only decrease the band gap but also introduce a mid-gap state into the catalyst electronic structure. The reports on its effect

vary. While some mid-gap states might promote photocatalytic activity, it seems that others can act as recombination centres, hindering the activity^{52,53}. Doping the catalyst, where co-doping offers the best results⁷², deposition of a co-catalyst, which acts as an electron sink and prevents the charge recombination and promotes the charge transfer, or the so called Z-scheme photocatalysts, where a combination of photocatalysts is used to produce higher energy excited electrons, are the most promising trends. Recently, there have been studies where novel photocatalysts are identified by a purely *ab initio* approach, solidifying the importance of the theoretical search for new photocatalysts. A prime example of such a photocatalyst has been the discovery of g-C₃N₄, which has been in recent years investigated as a strong competitor to the traditional TiO₂. Other purely theoretical studies have hinted at other novel materials, such as B₄C₃¹²⁷.

5 Adsorption

As succinctly described by Sabatier, the interaction between the catalyst and the substrate must not be too strong nor too weak for optimal catalysis. Thus, we first turn our attention to the adsorption of CO₂ on catalytic surfaces, which is, for obvious reasons, theoretically the most thoroughly studied part of the reaction cascade.

CO₂ is an inert and very stable compound with a formation energy of -393.5 kJ mol⁻¹. Due to its geometry (O=C=O angle is 180°, C=O bond length is 1.16 Å), the molecule is not polar. While the reduction potential of CO₂/CO₂⁻ vs NHE is -2.22 V, it can be changed by adsorption (-1.98 V on anatase TiO₂(101))¹³⁰. In this section, we review the calculated adsorption values of CO₂ on different photoactive substrates.

Ye et al.¹³¹ studied its adsorption on In₂O₃. Three stable adsorption configurations were tested, the most stable one having an adsorption energy of -1.25 eV. The bond angle in CO₂ was reduced to 126° and

the bonds were elongated to 1.29 and 1.28 Å. The Bader charge analysis showed that the electron density moved from In_2O_3 to CO_2 .

Hahn et al.¹²⁵ investigated the CeO_2 (111) surface at different coverages and configurations. The monodentate, bidentate and linear CO_2 adsorption modes were investigated at coverages 1/9 ML, 1/2 ML, and 2/3 ML. At a 1/9 ML coverage, the monodentate configuration had the strongest interaction, followed by the bidentate and linear, with values of -0.31, -0.12, and 0.02 eV, respectively. In the monodentate configuration, the C=O bond length is elongated to 1.27 Å and the bond angle is 129.7°, while in the bidentate configuration the bond lengths of 1.22 and 1.30 Å and the bond angle of 129.2° manifest. In the linear configuration, no significant bond elongation or bending (O=C=O: 177.6°) is found due to weak interaction with the surface. At higher coverages (1/2 ML and 2/3 ML), the interaction of CO_2 is decreased because of the repulsion between the CO_2 molecules.

He et al.¹³⁰ conducted a theoretical study of CO_2 adsorption on a pristine and oxygen-vacant anatase (101) surface. On the pristine anatase surface, they identified four possible configurations of adsorbed CO_2 with two of them being favourable: a linear configuration and a bidentate one. In the linear configuration, the bonding strength was -0.20 eV and in the bidentate configuration -0.14 eV. Such low values, which are characteristic of physisorption, were attributed to the use of a vanilla PBE functional by the authors. The oxygen-deficient (reduced) anatase (101) surface proved a better alternative for photocatalysis with a more favourable interaction of CO_2 in the linear configuration (-1.09 eV) than in the bidentate configuration. In both cases, the molecule is bent as the oxygen from CO_2 is pushed towards the oxygen vacancy, decreasing the angle to 128.7° and elongating the bonds to 1.20 and 1.34 Å, respectively. The authors emphasize that the binding energies of O_2 and H_2O are even more favourable, meaning these species might compete for the oxygen vacancy sites, effectively poisoning the catalyst.

Liu et al.¹³² also investigated the adsorption of CO_2 on the oxygen-vacant anatase (101) surface. However, their calculations were done using the DFT+U approach. The strongest binding was found

for the linear configuration (-0.89 eV), while in the vertical configuration CO₂ binds somewhat less strongly (-0.65 eV). On the stable pristine TiO₂ (101) surface, the binding interaction is -0.45 eV. Qualitatively, the results match those of He et al.¹³⁰

Hammami et al.¹³³ conducted an extensive study on the (001) surfaces of different metal oxides (Ca, Sc, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni), systematically testing different adsorption modes: vertical, flat (the oxygen atoms above two metal cations, the carbon in the gap between the surface oxygen atoms), BA1 (C atop of the surface oxygen and the CO₂ oxygen atoms between two metal ions), and BA2 (C atop of the surface oxygen and the CO₂ oxygen atoms atop of the metal atom). In most cases, the flat configurations proved to be the most favourable for adsorption. However, there were some exceptions, such as FeO, which favoured BA2, or CaO with BA1. The strength of the adsorption spanned from 2.09 eV to 0.10 eV, as follows: Sc>V>Ti>Ca>>Cr>Fe>Co>Mn.

Jensen et al.¹³⁴ studied various MgO and CaO sites. The most favourable adsorption sites on MgO proved to be the step and corner (tridentate) with adsorption energies of -1.60 eV and -1.58 eV, respectively, followed by the corner bidentate configuration with an adsorption energy of -1.19 eV. The corner (monodentate) and step sites were also the most favourable on CaO with adsorption energies of -2.30 eV and -2.27 eV, respectively, followed by the corner (bidentate), corner (tridentate), and terrace site with values of -1.89, -1.70 and -1.00 eV respectively. As previously reported, the bonds in CO₂ were also elongated and the angle decreased.

Saputro et al.¹³⁵ reported the adsorption modes of CO₂ on Pd₆M clusters doped by transition metals (M=Ni, Cu, Pt, Rh, and Pd). It was determined that CO₂ binds in the bidentate configuration in all instances. The charge transfer analysis between the cluster and CO₂ showed a positive correlation between the amount of the charge transfer and the adsorption strength. In the cases of Ni and Cu, the adsorption is stronger (-0.43 eV, -0.47 eV, respectively) as the *d*-orbitals of the cluster interact with the LUMO orbital of CO₂. Consequently, the C=O bonds elongate and the molecule bends.

Cao et al.³⁴ investigated the adsorption on g-C₃N₄ supported Pd (100) and Pd (111) supported by. The investigation revealed that the Pd (111) surface binds CO₂ stronger than Pd (100). They also showed that the desorption of products plays a role in selectivity. Methanol has a lower adsorption energy on Pd (111) than on Pd (100), which could promote its production. Zhu et al., however,¹³⁶ thoroughly looked into the adsorption solely on g-C₃N₄, considering all possible sites and taking into account all possible orientations. They showed that the horizontal adsorption is preferred, although by a small margin (0.04 eV between the most stable vertical and horizontal adsorption). The adsorption interactions are -0.42 eV or less.

The adsorption energies of CO₂ on pristine and defective Zn₂GeO₄ were studied by Liu et al.¹²⁴ using the PW91 GGA approach. For the pristine surface, the (010) and (001) planes were studied because they are the most common and active. Five different CO₂ configurations were chosen and studied: vertical, horizontal (monodentate), bidentate and two bridge configurations (the carbon atom bent towards the surface or outwards). On the (010) plane, the most stable was the bridge configuration (inwards) with an adsorption energy of -1.04 eV, followed by the bidentate configuration (-0.91 eV). For the (001) plane, the bridge (inwards) configuration was the most stable with an adsorption energy of -1.12 eV. In all cases, the bonds were elongated and the molecule was bent as the electron density flowed from Zn₂GeO₄ towards CO₂. Introducing an oxygen vacancy slightly increases the adsorption interaction by 0.14 and 0.24 eV for the (010) and (001) surfaces, respectively. It is possible to heal the oxygen vacancy by the dissociative adsorption of CO₂.

An interesting material is boron in the B₈₀ fullerene structure, which has a great potential for metal-free photocatalysis. Qu et al. studied the adsorption of CO₂ on B₈₀¹³⁷ and compared three possible adsorption modes. In all instances, one oxygen was bound in the bidentate configuration. As B₈₀ consists of both acidic and basic sites¹³⁸, CO₂, being a Lewis acid, can interact strongly with the basic sites of B₈₀. This is confirmed by the strong adsorption energies in all three configurations (-0.64, -0.64, and -0.62 eV). As discussed later on, the authors also showed that B₈₀ can function as an efficient catalyst for the production of HCOOH.

As shown, adsorption depends on several parameters, namely the catalyst structure, doping or presence of co-catalyst, the surface facet and defects (e.g. oxygen vacancies). The general trends demonstrate that horizontal adsorption is favoured over vertical ¹³², whereas oxygen vacancies, depositions of co-catalysts and doping increase the adsorption strength relative to pristine surfaces ¹³⁰. Lower surface coverages result in increased interactions due to a weaker repulsion between neighbouring CO₂ molecules ¹²⁵. When CO₂ is activated upon adsorption (Figure 3), which is evidenced by the elongation of the bond (decrease of the bond order) and the electron transfer from the catalyst to the LUMO of CO₂ (Figure 4) ^{139,140}, it bends the molecule by the excess electron density.

Figure 3: Visual representation of the B₈₀ cluster and different types of CO₂ adsorption on its surface.

Color code: pink – B, gray – C, red – O. Reprinted with permission from ¹³⁸. Copyright (2014)

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Figure 4: a) HOMO and b) LUMO of gaseous CO_2 ; c) HOMO and d) LUMO of B_{80} ; e) HOMO and f) LUMO of chemisorbed CO_2 on B_{80} in the most stable configuration. Color code: pink – B, gray – C, red – O. Reprinted with permission from ¹³⁸. Copyright (2014) American Chemical Society.

Adsorption and a consequent activation of the CO_2 molecule is an important first step in the reaction. The interaction of other species with the catalyst (i.e. adsorption/desorption) also plays a significant role in determining the selectivity and should not go unmentioned. If intermediates bind too weakly they can desorb before being converted to the final products. Conversely, the final products should not bind too strongly to avoid further conversion or reverse reactions. This was demonstrated by Cao et al. ³⁴ who studied the photoreduction of CO_2 on Pd(100) and Pd(111) on g- C_3N_4 . They found that the adsorption interaction of methanol on Pd(100) is 10-times stronger than on the Pd(111) surface, making desorption from Pd(111) much faster. Since the methane desorption energies are comparable on both surfaces, they concluded that Pd(111) is most likely more selective towards methanol. Similarly, Qu et al. ¹³⁷ demonstrated the importance of the adsorption interaction of products on B_{80} fullerene. Their results indicated that CO binds very strongly and is highly unlikely to be a major product, while CH_4 , CH_3OH and HCOOH display a weaker adsorption. Combining that with the limiting potentials, they concluded that HCOOH is favored. The product distribution is highly dependent on the desorption rates of intermediates and products. Weaker adsorption of important intermediates, such as CO and HCOOH ,

might prevent the formation of hydrocarbons due to their tendency of desorption from the surface, whereas stronger adsorption may imply that no CO and HCOOH is produced. Adsorption is an important step, which is not only dependent on the catalyst and its modifications but on the exposed surface.

Table 1: A review of calculated band gap values for most promising photocatalysts and comparison with experimental values.

Catalyst	Functional	Theoretical band gap [eV]	Experimental band gap [eV]	References	
TiO ₂ rutile	PBE-GGA	1.782	3.03	72	
	DFT+U	2.2			
TiO ₂ anatase	PBE-GGA	2.532	3.20		
	DFT+U	2.5			
TiO ₂ amorphous	PBE-GGA	2.1	3.40		
	DFT+U	2.5			
TiO ₂ anatase	PBE-GGA	2.00	3.20		141
		3.08			
N-doped TiO ₂	PBE-GGA+U	2.77			
Fe-doped TiO ₂		2.76			
N,Fe-codoped TiO ₂		2.73			
TiO ₂ rutile	PBE-GGA	1.77	3.1	142	
	HSE06	3.05			
anatase TiO ₂ (101)	HSE	3.05		143	
Pt/TiO ₂		3.06			
Pd/TiO ₂		3.05			
Rh/TiO ₂		2.80			
Ru/TiO ₂		3.10			
GaP(100)/TiO ₂ (001)	HSE06 (PBE-GGA)	1.50		128	
Ag ₃ PO ₄ (111)/g-C ₃ N ₄	PBE0	2.52		45	
Ag ₃ PO ₄		2.47			
Ag ₃ PO ₄ (111)		2.75			
g-C ₃ N ₄	HSE06	2.75			

g-C ₃ N ₄ monolayer		3.13		
g-C ₃ N ₄	HSE06	2.98	2.70	38
Pd/g-C ₃ N ₄		0.64		
Pt/g-C ₃ N ₄		0.72		
g-C ₃ N ₄			2.74	
1%KBH-C ₃ N ₄	HSE06		2.66	126
2%KBH-C ₃ N ₄			2.55	
3%KBH-C ₃ N ₄			2.35	
5%KBH-C ₃ N ₄			1.74	
S-g-C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA	1.18	2.55	31
S-g-C ₃ N ₄	HSE06	2.42	2.55	129
g-C ₃ N ₄		2.80	2.70	
g-C ₃ N ₄ monolayer	HSE06	2.76	2.7	144
CdS		2.36	2.4	
CdS(110)		2.36		
g-C ₃ N ₄ /CdS(110)		2.02		
B ₄ C ₃ monolayer	HSE06	2.39		127
Zn ₂ GeO ₄	PW91-GGA	2	4.50	124
ZnS wurtzite	PW91-GGA	2.09	3.6-3.8	145
ZnS sphalerite		2.08		
ZnS wurtzite (S-vacancy)		1.30		
ZnS sphalerite (S-vacancy)		1.72		
ZnO	PBE-GGA	0.73	3.2	146
N-doped ZnO		0.58		
C-doped ZnO		0.16		
S-doped ZnO		0.55		
ZnS	PBE-GGA	1.92	3.1	147
Zn _{0.9} Cd _{0.1} S		1.66	3	
Zn _{0.7} Cd _{0.3} S		1.40	2.76	
Zn _{0.6} Cd _{0.4} S		1.46	2.57	
Zn _{0.5} Cd _{0.5} S		1.36	2.45	
Zn _{0.4} Cd _{0.6} S		1.28	2.42	
Zn _{0.3} Cd _{0.7} S		1.28	2.35	
Zn _{0.1} Cd _{0.9} S		1.18	2.33	
CdS		1.15	2.3	
ZnSnN ₂ (bulk)	PBE-GGA	0.11		148
ZnSnN ₂ (monolayer)		0.65		
ZnSnN ₂ (bilayer)		0.93		
ZnSnN ₂ (bulk)	PBE0	1.79		
ZnSnN ₂ (monolayer)		2.39		

ZnSnN ₂ (bilayer)		2.62		
SiAs (monolayer)	PBE-GGA	1.79		149
GeAs (monolayer)		1.44		
SnAs (monolayer)		1.10		
SiAs (monolayer)	HSE06	2.35		
GeAs (monolayer)		2.08		
SnAs (monolayer)		1.69		
MoS ₂ (monolayer)	PBE-GGA	1.25	1.8	150
CdS		2.17	2.42	
MoS ₂ /CdS		1.02		
MoS ₂ (monolayer)	HSE06	1.78	1.8	
CdS		2.41	2.42	
MoS ₂ /CdS		2.11		
MnO	DFT+U/G0W0	4.13	3.90	151
FeO		2.30	2.40	
Fe ₂ O ₃		3.08	2.60	
NiO		3.60	4.00	
Cu ₂ O		2.17	2.10	
MnO	LDA	0.57	3.5-4.3	152
	PBE	0.93		
	PBE+U	1.68		
	HSE	3.82		
	PBE0	4.04		
CeO ₂ (111)	DFT+U	1.99		125
	PBE	2		
BiOBr	PBE-GGA	2.31	2.7	153
Bi ₃ O ₄ Br		2.17	2.4	
SnS ₂ monolayer	PBE	1.57	2.23	154
	HSE06	2.52		
	G0W0	2.88		

6 Reaction mechanisms

CO₂ can be reduced to several carbon-containing species, such as CO, HCOOH, CH₃OH or CH₄. From the thermodynamic point of view, the formation of multielectron reduced species is easier than the formation of CO₂⁻, which is exploited in electrocatalysis. However, kinetics also plays an important role in the product distribution. The reduction potentials (vs SHE at pH=7 and 25 °C) are, as follows:

The reduction potential at the catalyst must be lower than the desired product for the reaction to proceed as depicted in Figure 5. As seen in the above overall net reactions, different species require a different amount of electrons to be formed.

Figure 5: Reduction potentials for different products and corresponding reduction/oxidation potentials from several photocatalysts. Reprinted with permission from Ref. ¹⁵⁵.

The process consists of several elementary steps and is rather complex (*vide infra*). Another important aspect of the reaction mechanism is the choice of the reducing agent. The most commonly used ones are H₂O and H₂; however, sometimes CH₄ and CH₃OH are also used ^{14,156,157}. H₂O has the obvious advantage of high abundance and low price and is therefore widely used. However, it has a few disadvantages, such as competitive reactions (water splitting) ¹⁵⁸ due to its high adsorption affinity, covering many active sites and hindering the reduction of CO₂ ¹⁵⁹. The oxygen released from the oxidation of water can also retard its photocatalytic ability and even help form CO₂ ¹⁶⁰.

A possible solution might be to use H₂, which yields similar products through a different mechanism depending on the reaction system. Because no oxygen is produced, the H₂ pathway also enables higher yields ¹⁶¹. The reaction mechanism, pathway, kinetics, and products are of course specific to each studied system.

Table 2: Most common catalyst/reactant combinations for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction and corresponding products.

Reactant	Catalyst	Products	Production [$\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$]	Selectivity	Reference
H ₂	10wt%MMT/TiO ₂	CO CH ₄ C ₂ H ₆	25.95	98% CO	162
H ₂ , heat (190°C)	In ₂ O _{3-x} (OH) _y	CO	153		18
H ₂ , heat (170°C)	ncSI:H	CO	17		163
H ₂	0.1wt%Pd/Nb ₂ O ₅	CO	1880	99.5% CO	23
	10wt%Pd/Nb ₂ O ₅	CO CH ₄	750 110		
H ₂ , heat (150°C)	0.03%Bi/ In ₂ O _{3-x} (OH) _y	CO	1.32		164
H ₂ O(g)	S-doped g- C ₃ N ₄	CH ₃ OH	1.12		31
	undoped g-C ₃ N ₄	CH ₃ OH	0.81		
H ₂ O(g)	Pd(100) g- C ₃ N ₄	CH ₄ CH ₃ OH	0.29 2.23		34
	Pd(111) g-C ₃ N ₄	CH ₄ CH ₃ OH	0.4 3.17		
H ₂ O(g)	2.5%CuInS ₂ /TiO ₂	CH ₄	2.5		165
		CH ₃ OH	0.86		
H ₂ O	C/Pt/In ₂ O ₃	CO	126.6		79
		CH ₄	27.9		
H ₂ O	0.5%GDY/TiO ₂	CO	50.53		166
		CH ₄	30.92		
H ₂ O	1% Pt/TiO ₂	CH ₄	4.6		167
H ₂ O(g)	1.5%Ag/TiO ₂	CH ₄	1.5		24
H ₂ O	1.5%Ag/TiO ₂	CH ₃ OH	4.5		
H ₂ O(g)	Au/TiO ₂	CH ₄	2.52		168
		C ₂ H ₆	1.67		
H ₂ O(g)	5%Pg- C ₃ N ₄ /Sn ₂ S ₃ - DETA	CH ₄	4.93		169
		CH ₃ OH	1.35		
H ₂ O	Bi ₂ MoO ₆ NS	CO	3.62		17
H ₂ O	Bi ₂₄ O ₃₁ Cl ₁₀	CO	0.9		55
H ₂ O	3%KBH-C ₃ N ₄	CO	1.19		126
		CH ₄	0.63		
H ₂ O	CeO _x -S/ZnIn ₂ S ₄	CO	180		28
H ₂ O	4.6% Au/ZnO	CH ₄ C ₂ H ₆	21 27		170
	1.7% Ag/ZnO	CH ₄	25		
	1.9% Pd/ZnO	CH ₄	18		

In Table 2, we list the most commonly used photocatalysts for the reduction of CO₂ with H₂ or H₂O and the obtained products. However, the challenge remains to postulate a single reaction mechanism to describe the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂. Most research is focused primarily on the experimental determination of catalyst properties and yields.

Cao et al.³⁴ investigated the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ on Pd/g-C₃N₄ and calculated the adsorption energies. By means of FTIR, they proposed a simple reaction mechanism, which suggested that electrons accumulate on the Pd particles. They react with the adsorbed CO₂ molecule to form HCOOH, HCHO, CH₃OH and CH₄ in this order. The final product can be very dependent on the exposed surface of the Pd nanoparticles. As methanol appears to have a lower adsorption energy on the Pd (111) plane than on Pd (100), it can desorb more easily before it can react further to CH₄, increasing the selectivity towards CH₃OH. However, the kinetics was determined purely experimentally and no attempt at identifying any transition states was made.

Gao et al.³⁸ researched Pd/g-C₃N₄ and Pt/g-C₃N₄ solely from the theoretical perspective, treating Pd and Pt as single atoms, which significantly reduces the band gap (from 2.98 eV to 0.64 eV and 0.72 eV, respectively) and depresses the conduction-band minimum to -0.9 eV, which is more negative than of CO₂/HCOOH, CO₂/CH₃OH, and CO₂/CH₄. They used the PBE functional with Grimme's empirical corrections (HSE06 was used for the band structures and optical absorption spectra). They calculated the complete potential energy surface along with all transition states for the hydrogenation of CO₂. In this study, the metal atoms function as the active sites while g-C₃N₄ serves as the source of hydrogen. On Pd/g-C₃N₄, HCOOH and some CH₃OH are predominantly formed, while on Pt/g-C₃N₄ methane forms. In both cases, the proposed reaction pathway follows the following intermediates CO₂ → HCOO → HCOOH → HCO → CH₂O → CH₂OH. It can then dissociate to CH₂ and through CH₃ yield CH₄ or hydrogenate to CH₃OH. On Pd/g-C₃N₄, the first rate-determining step is the formation of HCOOH (0.46 eV), which then desorbs. For the production of CH₃OH, the calculated reaction barrier is 1.43 eV for the formation of HCO from HCOOH and 1.46 eV for the formation of CH₃OH from CH₂OH. Thus, HCOOH is predicted to be the main product. On Pt/g-C₃N₄, the barriers are lower than any desorption

energy and CH₂OH forms, which then follows the route CH₂ → CH₃ → CH₄. The hydrogenation of HCOO into HCOOH is the rate limiting step in this pathway with a value of 1.01 eV.

Wang et al.¹²⁶ proposed a mechanism for the photoreduction of CO₂ on 3 % KBH-C₃N₄ based on their experimental work (DRIFT, FTIR, UV-Vis). They determined CO₂⁻, HCO₃⁻, CO₃²⁻ and HCOO as the intermediates on both pristine C₃N₄ and 3 % KBH-C₃N₄ and postulated the following mechanism: CO₂ is reduced to CO₂⁻, which can react into HCO₃⁻ (with OH), CO and CO₃²⁻ (with CO₂⁻), CO and OH⁻ or HCOOH. HCOOH can be further dehydrogenated into HCOO, which can dissociate into CO (and OH). CO can desorb or react further. The C=O bond can be broken (the carbene pathway¹⁷¹), producing C and OH in the presence of H⁺ and e⁻. C is then sequentially hydrogenated CH → CH₂ → CH₃ → CH₄. The major products of the reaction are thus CO and CH₄. The mechanism, however, was not supported theoretically.

Using PBE-GGA based DFT with Grimme's correction (D2), Wang et al.¹²⁹ theoretically studied sulphur-doped g-C₃N₄ nanosheets because sulphur enhances their catalytic performance based on electronic and optical properties calculations. For the band gap, PDOS and absorption spectra calculations, the HSE06 hybrid functional was used. The sulphur doping was found to decrease the band gap from 2.80 eV to 2.42 eV. While in g-C₃N₄ the Fermi level adjoins the VB, in the doped catalyst the Fermi level moves to the bottom of CB, as in an *n*-type doping system. While investigating the reaction pathway, the authors calculated the Gibbs free energies of the species involved in the reaction. They postulated three reaction pathways, the most probable being: CO₂, COOH, CO, HCO, HCHO, CH₃OH. The rate determining step was CO₂ → COOH with Δ*G* = 1.15 eV.

Another study on g-C₃N₄ was done by Azofra et al.¹⁷², where they studied the reaction mechanism of the CO₂ reduction using PBE-GGA with Grimme's correction (D3). They first examined the stability of planar versus corrugated g-C₃N₄ and showed that the latter was thermodynamically more stable by 2.91 eV. The investigation of the reaction mechanism on the planar and corrugated surfaces yielded the following reaction mechanism: CO₂ → HOCO → CO → HCO → H₂CO → CH₃O → CH₃OH. The rate

limiting step in the planar configuration was found to be the first hydrogenation of CO₂ to HOCO with $\Delta G^{298\text{ K}} = 1.64\text{ eV}$, while on the corrugated surface it was significantly lower at $\Delta G^{298\text{ K}} = 1.15\text{ eV}$. The rate limiting step on the corrugated surface was H₂CO → CH₃O with $\Delta G^{298\text{ K}} = 1.21\text{ eV}$. Planar g-C₃N₄ therefore requires higher overpotentials to initiate the reaction but then quickly reacts towards methanol, while on the corrugated surface it is more likely to see earlier products such as CO (at lower overpotentials). The authors also investigated how the solvent, namely water, affects the reaction mechanism on the corrugated surface. In an aqueous medium, the barrier for the first hydrogenation step is reduced from 1.15 eV to 0.99 eV, while for the step H₂CO → CH₃O it increases from 1.21 eV to 1.59 eV.

The reduction of CO₂ on the B₄C₃ monolayer supported on Si was theoretically studied by Chang et al. using the GGA-PBE approach (or HSE06 for band gap calculations).¹²⁷ The authors first checked that the monolayer is thermodynamically and kinetically stable, calculating the phonon dispersion and cohesive energy, and performing ab initio molecular dynamics. As the B₄C₃ monolayer can be viewed as an infinite lattice of the B₄C₃H₆ molecules (with a tetracoordinated carbon atom in the middle), the electronic structure of the molecule was analysed. The calculations of the band structure, the projected density of states, dielectric constants, optical absorption, carrier mobilities and band edge alignments showed that B₄C₃ is a promising material for photocatalysis. The authors calculated that the one-electron reduction of CO₂ (to yield CO₂⁻) occurs at -1.90 V. However, the proton-coupled conversion of CO₂ requires much more modest potentials: -0.61 V to yield HCOOH and -0.52 V to yield CO (and H₂O). The mechanistic evaluation revealed that CO₂ first hydrogenates to HCOO, then to HCOOH, HCO, CHOH, CH₂OH, CH₂, CH₃ and ultimately CH₄. The rate limiting step of the reaction is the dehydroxylation of HCOOH to HCO, with a barrier of $G = 0.63\text{ eV}$ at 25 °C and 1 atm.

The reaction mechanism of the reduction of CO₂ over Ag₃PO₄(111)/g-C₃N₄ was theoretically studied by Tafreshi et al.⁴⁵ using the GGA-PBE approach with Grimme's correction (D3). For the electronic properties, hybrid PBE0 and HSE0 were used. They showed that CO₂ is step-wise reduced and can yield HCOOH, CH₂O, CH₄ or CH₃OH. The authors focused on reaction energies (and not barriers) and

investigated the complete reaction pathway with all possible intermediates. For the production of methanol, the following mechanism was proposed: $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{HCOO} \rightarrow t\text{-COOH} \rightarrow c\text{-COOH} \rightarrow \text{HCOOH} \rightarrow \text{HCO} \rightarrow t\text{-HCOH} \rightarrow c\text{-HCOH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$. The methane pathway branches off at $\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$. The authors also considered a different mechanism proceeding through HOCO , which is thermodynamically less favourable. Based on the thermodynamics of the end products, the authors propose that CH_4 is more likely to form than CH_3OH . They also proposed a general reaction pathway for the CO_2 reduction as depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Proposed reaction mechanism with several possible pathways for photocatalytic CO_2 reduction, reprinted with permission from reference ⁴⁵. Copyright (2019) American Chemical Society.

In their B₈₀ fullerene study, Qu et al.¹³⁷ also proposed a tentative mechanism for the reduction of CO₂, which yields HCOOH, HCHO or CH₄. As CO₂ can bind to the fullerene in three configurations, they constructed three potential energy surfaces. In all instances, HCOOH was the predominant product with a limiting potential of -0.18 V. Based on thermodynamic considerations (no transition states or kinetics were calculated), CO₂ is reduced to HCOOH via the O=CH-O* intermediate. The formation of more reduced products was deemed less likely.

The reduction of CO₂ was also theoretically studied by Homlaimai et al.²¹ who studied non-noble metal single-atom catalysts (Fe, Co, Ni) on g-C₃N₄ using the GGA-PBE approach with Grimme's correction (D3). They proposed the following mechanism CO₂ → HCOO → HCOOH and included the transition states in their study. For the first step (yielding formate), the barriers for the reaction were 0.22, 0.60, 1.13, and 0.70 eV on Fe-g-C₃N₄, Co-g-C₃N₄, Ni-g-C₃N₄, Cu-g-C₃N₄, respectively. In the second hydrogenation step to form formic acid (HCOOH), the barriers were 0.58, 0.72, 0.34 and 0.02 eV, respectively. Thus, the rate-determining step was the second step for Fe-g-C₃N₄ and Co-g-C₃N₄ and the first step for Ni-g-C₃N₄ and Cu-g-C₃N₄. The authors conclude that the activity follows the order: Fe-g-C₃N₄ > Co-g-C₃N₄ > Cu-g-C₃N₄ > Ni-g-C₃N₄.

Zhao et al.¹⁷⁰ investigated the reaction mechanism for the CO₂ conversion over noble metals (Au, Ag, Pd) on 3D porous ZnO nanosheets. The authors performed experimental testing and theoretical calculations using the GGA-PBE approach with Grimme's correction (D2). Four reaction mechanisms involving a step-wise hydrogenation of CO₂ were studied: (i) CO₂ → HCOO* → H₂COO* → H₂COOH* → H₂CO* → H₃COH* → H₃C* → CH₄, (ii) CO₂ → H₂COOH* → H₃COOH* → H₃CO* → H₃COH* → H₄COH* → CH₄, (iii) CO₂ → H₃COOH* → H₃CO* → H₃COH* → H₃C* → CH₄, (iv) CO₂ → H₂COOH* → H₂CO* → H₃COH* → H₄COH* → CH₄. Additionally, two cross-hydrogenation processes on O and C atoms were also studied: (v) CO₂ → COOH* → CO → HCO* → H₂CO* → H₃CO* → H₃COH* → H₄COH* → CH₄ and (vi) CO₂ → H₃COH* → H₃C* → CH₄. The authors focused on the energetics of the stable intermediates only and did not study the barriers. On bare ZnO nanosheets, the pathway (iii) is the most favourable. However, once loaded with metals, the

reaction pathway (ν) also becomes most achievable. This explains why CO and CH₄ concomitantly form. The dehydroxylation of COOH* and H₂COOH* is the rate-determining step, which determines which pathway is predominantly followed. The selectivity can be tuned by balancing between the thermodynamically and kinetically controlled products. On the Pd catalyst, the difference in endothermicity of the dehydroxylation of H₂COOH* and COOH* is the greatest, explaining the high selectivity to CH₄ of Pd-supported catalysts. On the silver catalyst, the formation of CO is preferred. On Au/ZnO, C₂H₆ also forms experimentally but was not theoretically modelled. This reaction is possible by a further conversion CH₄ into C₂H₆ by a dehydrogenative coupling mechanism.³⁶

Li et al. investigated the photoreduction of CO₂ on thin TiO₂-coated GaP, which solves the problem of poor stability of pure GaP.¹²⁸ With the modified phenomenological theory of Martensitic crystallography and a stochastic surface walking global search, the structure of the interface was resolved on the atomic level as consisting of the (001)TiO₂//(100)GaP, (101)TiO₂//(110)GaP, and (112)TiO₂//(100)GaP junctions with negligible interface strain. The authors showed that the electrons from GaP readily tunnel through a sufficiently thin TiO₂ level, which is responsible for the decrease of the CO₂ reduction barrier from 1.02 eV. While the authors focused mostly on the interface structure and its electronic properties, they also briefly deal with the reaction mechanism. They purport the following mechanism: CO₂ → HCOOH → H₂CO → CH₃OH with the corresponding activation barriers 1.84, 1.82, and 1.24 eV, respectively, when one does not account for quantum tunnelling. When accounted for, the barriers are lowered to more feasible 0.82, 0.80, and 0.28 eV, respectively.

Defective and pristine (oxygen vacancy) TiO₂ surfaces and the reaction mechanisms thereon were theoretically studied by Ji et al.¹⁷³ To correctly describe the photogenerated holes and trapped electrons, a combined GGA+U/HSE approach was used. The geometries were optimised on the GGA+U PBE level and then single point HSE calculations were performed. The authors proposed two tentative mechanisms: fast hydrogenation (CO₂ → CO → CH₂O → CH₃OH → CH₃ → CH₄) and fast deoxygenation (CO₂ → CO → C → CH₂ → CH₃ → CH₄/CH₃OH). The oxygen vacancy was found to be more active than the Ti atoms for the reaction at hand. Based on the calculated transition state

barriers, the authors argue that the fast-deoxygenation pathway is unlikely (the key intermediate C* will not form). Instead, a combined mechanism stemming from the fast-dehydrogenation is proposed: $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4/\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$. The rate-determining steps are the reduction of H_2CO to CH_3O (1.26 eV) and the CO_2 dissociation to CO (1.04 eV or 0.73 eV, depending on the orientation). Due to their strong interaction with the surface, H_2CO and HCOOH are not liberated but react further.

The reaction mechanisms were studied on a pristine anatase TiO_2 (101) surface by Ji et al.¹⁷⁴ using PBE+U for geometry optimizations and performing single-point HSE calculations for energetics. The authors propose two possible reaction mechanisms (i) $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{HCOOH} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$ and (ii) $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$. In (i), the rate limiting step is the photoreduction of $\text{HCOOH} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO}$ with a barrier of 1.81 eV, while in (ii) the rate limiting step is the dissociation $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}$ with a barrier of 1.41 eV. Experimental results show that both routes are active. The oxygen vacancies seem to shift the reaction mechanism from the first pathway, which is typical of the pristine surface, to the second pathway. The authors thus propose a combined reaction mechanism (iii) $\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{CH}_4$.

Liu et al.¹³² also studied the on an oxygen-vacant anatase TiO_2 (101) surface using the DFT+U approach with the PBE functional and the Thatchenko-Scheffler dispersion correction. They showed that after adsorbing on the vacancy site, the CO_2 molecule dissociates to CO and O , filling the oxygen vacancy. The ensuing CO can only bind to another oxygen vacancy and not to the pristine surface. Interestingly, CO_2 can bind in two configurations (vertical and horizontal), of which the horizontal one is more favorable (adsorption energies of -0.89 eV and -0.63 eV, respectively). However, the barrier for the formation of CO from the horizontal configuration of adsorbed CO_2 is 0.74 eV, but only 0.15 eV from the vertical initial configuration. CO is preferentially bound as a monodentate species, which then proceeds through the $\text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{CHOH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$. CO can also bind as a bidentate species, which is reduced as $\text{HCO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$. The formation of methanol is not expected as its desorption energy is 1.66 eV, while the corresponding reaction barrier for the

aliphatics) and the reduction of CO₂ by different reductants. The choice of the reductant also influences the product ratio considerably, which the authors describe in their general mechanism. While the first product in all cases is CO, possible subsequent products include methane and higher hydrocarbons, methanol, ethanol, formic acid, acetic acid, and acetone.¹⁷⁵ In Figures 6 and 7, the theoretical mechanism is depicted. The products obtained in a particular set-up depend on the catalyst used (material, thickness, surface treatment, facets, defects), the conditions and the reactants.

Three main reaction mechanisms are proposed. If CO₂ undergoes dissociative adsorption, the ensuing CO is hydrogenated via the fast hydrogenation route through CH₂O to CH₃OH or CH₄. This mechanism is feasible when oxygen vacancies are present on the surface, such as in the O-lean TiO₂. Most photocatalysts, however, hydrogenate CO₂ to either HCOO (the formate route) or COOH. The former mechanism is generally favoured on catalysts with metals (Pt/g-C₃N₄), while the latter occurs more rarely on some less noble metals or non-metal catalysts. Nevertheless, both mechanism *can* play a non-negligible part during photocatalysis and should be considered. The summary on the investigation methodologies on several catalysts and the results are gathered in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of theoretical studies of photocatalysts.

Catalyst	Method (functional)	Excited states accounted for	Investigated	Proposed reaction mechanism	Electronic structures calculated	Reference
GaP(100)/TiO ₂ (001)	PBE-GGA	pseudo (emulated with increased H* coverage)	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOOH → H ₂ CO → CH ₃ OH	orientation relations, DOS, band gap,	128
anatase TiO ₂ (101) oxygen vacant	PBE-GGA+U/HSE	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOOH, CO → CH ₂ O → CH ₃ OH → CH ₃ OH → CH ₃		173
				CO ₂ → CO → CH ₂ O → CH ₃ O → CH ₃ → CH ₃ OH		
anatase TiO ₂ (101)	DFT+U	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → CO → CHO → CHOH → CH ₂ OH → CH ₃ OH/CH ₄	adsorption energies	132
				CO ₂ → CO → CHO → CH ₂ O → CH ₃ OH → CH ₃ OH/CH ₄		
Pd/g-C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOOH → HCHO → CH ₃ OH → CH ₄	adsorption energies	34
Pd/g- C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA+ Grimme D3	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOO → HCOOH → HCO → CH ₂ O → CH ₂ OH → CH ₃ OH	band gap, adsorption energies, CBM/VBM	38
Pt/g- C ₃ N ₄				CO ₂ → HCOO → HCOOH → HCO → CH ₂ O → CH ₂ OH → CH ₂ → CH ₃ → CH ₄		
g- C ₃ N ₄						
g- C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA	no	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCO ₃ , HCOOH, CO	HOMO/LUMO, band gap	126
1% KBH- C ₃ N ₄				CO → C → CH → CH ₂ → CH ₃ → CH ₄		
2% KBH- C ₃ N ₄						
3% KBH- C ₃ N ₄						
5% KBH- C ₃ N ₄						
Ag ₃ PO ₄ (111)/g- C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA+Grimme D3	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOO → t,c-COOH → HCOOH → HCO → t,c-HCOH → CH ₂ O → CH ₂ OH → CH ₂ → CH ₃ → CH ₄ CO ₂ → t,c-COOH → tt-HOCO → COH → t-HCOH → CH ₂ O → CH ₂ → CH ₃ → CH ₄	adsorption energies, DOS, charge density differences	45

					band gap, CBM/VBM	
g- C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA+ GrimmeD3	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOO → HCOOH	adsorption energies, DOS, Bader charge analysis	21
Fe/g- C ₃ N ₄						
Co/g- C ₃ N ₄						
Cu/g- C ₃ N ₄						
Ni/g- C ₃ N ₄						
g- C ₃ N ₄	PBE-GGA+ GrimmeD3	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HOCO → CO → HCO → H ₂ CO → CH ₃ O → CH ₃ OH	DOS, reductant environment, electron localization function	172
B ₄ C ₃	PBE-GGA + Grimme correction	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HCOO → HCO → CHOH → CH ₂ OH → CH ₂ → CH ₃ → CH ₄	HOMO/LUMO, band gap, thermodynamic stability, adsorption, CBM/VBM, Carrier mobilities, charge density differences	127
B ₈₀ fullerene	PBE-GGA +Grimme D2	no	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → HOCO → HCOOH	Charge difference diagram, adsorption energies	137
ZnO NSs	PBE-GGA + GrimmeD2	not explicitly	reaction pathway	CO ₂ → H ₂ COOH → H ₂ CO → H ₃ COH → H ₄ COH → CH ₄	adsorption energies, charge density difference	170
Au/ZnO NSs						
Ag/ZnO NSs						
Pd/ZnO NSs						
In ₂ O ₃	B3LYP	LR-TDDFT		CO ₂ +H ₂ → CO+ H ₂ O	HOMO/LUMO,	176

7 Kinetic modelling and macroscale simulations

Current research in modelling disproportionately focuses on individual reaction steps, such as adsorbate adsorption, light absorption or surface reactions. Instead, a coupled microkinetic model is required for a thorough understanding of the process and its improvements. Unfortunately, not many attempts to describe the photoreduction on a microkinetic scale and couple it with CFD have been made. Although they are mostly limited to simple systems, such as CO oxidation, some do study CO₂ photoreduction. Much more common are multiscale efforts on thermocatalytic CO₂ reduction.^{177,178}

Hammerschmidt et al.¹⁷⁹ studied the CO₂ photoreduction to formic acid on anatase TiO₂ in a multiscale manner. From the Wulff construction, the most prominent facets were discovered to be (101) and (100). To perform kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) simulations on the (101) surface, thermodynamic parameters (adsorption energies, reaction energies) were procured from the literature and cast into a kMC model. To make the model tractable, several assumptions had to be made (charge transport not considered, holes assumed to react instantaneously, formic acid being the only product). According to the model, inhomogeneous light absorption has an effect on the photocatalytic activity. It was apparent that the illumination intensity and the particle size have a significant impact on the reactivity; namely, smaller particles (40 nm) are efficient but larger particles (145 nm) exhibit higher reactivity.

Few attempts have dealt with the scale-up of the CO₂ photoreduction, mostly due to low conversions and economic viability at present prices. In a study by Chueh et al.¹⁸⁰, a solar-driven CO₂ reduction in a solar cavity-receiver reactor was investigated. However, the governing mechanism of the reaction was a thermocatalytic conversion with solar energy heating. The cerium oxide catalyst displayed stability and high activity over 500 cycles. The efficiency and the cycling rates were mostly limited by thermal losses (conduction, radiation). A realistic application of such a system is feasible due to the low cost of the cerium oxide catalyst and its longevity (exceeding 500 cycles).

CO oxidation is a more commonly studied reaction due its simplicity. As shown by Matera et. al in a treatment of a *thermocatalytic* reaction, it is possible to link a first-principle kinetic Monte Carlo model (with DFT-supplied data) with computational fluid dynamics. ^{181,182}

While the theoretical description of the photoreduction itself, combined with the quest for better catalytic materials, has garnered a lot of attention, the other side of the process has remained largely overlooked. The efficiency can be greatly increased with an engineering approach and designing better photoreactor systems. The efficiency is governed by the number of phases involved (gas-solid, gas-liquid-solid), mode of operation (batch, continuous) and catalyst bed (fixed, fluidized).

In addition to *ab initio* methods and catalyst development, the design and optimization of reactors for the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction is of crucial importance. The reactors can be classified based on the phases involved (two- or three-phase systems) and mode of operation into three categories: slurry, fixed bed and membrane reactors. Slurry reactors utilize a high surface area but mass transfer limitations, low light utilization, and post-process separation often make them uneconomical. Fixed-bed reactors offer high conversion rates, low pressure drops and no cost of separation of the catalyst from the products, but the utilization of photons and coating of the catalyst on the bed surface is problematic. Membrane photo-reactors, although exhibiting high yields and selectivities, suffer from low efficiency due to the limited mobility of the charge carriers, as well as mass transfer limitations. For more information, the reader is referred the review by Khan et al. ¹²¹

For a complete description of the macro scale, mass and heat transfer has to be taken into account. Braham et al. ¹⁸³ used CFD to study a fluidized bed photoreactor in a complete multi-scale simulation using integrated particle, fluid and photo behavior models. The results show that fluidized bed photoreactors should either have very narrow, dense particle beds and small reaction volumes, or larger reaction volumes with a more distributed solids phase. A novel photon absorption behavior was discovered.

A different study in a twin bubbling reactor for CO₂ photoreduction was performed by Chu et al.¹⁸⁴ They made several assumptions regarding the reaction and transport phenomena for the purpose of simplicity (e.g. the photocatalytic reaction rate is only a function of time and not position in the reactor, the gas phase is considered an ideal gas and the density is a constant). Such assumptions might introduce some discrepancies because light distribution in the reactor is not homogenous, but rather light dispersion can cause heterogeneities in the reactor, making the position of the particles in the reactor crucial^{183,185,186}. The CFD simulations demonstrated that the bubbling twin reactor outperforms the traditional twin reactor in mass transfer, as well as production. Increasing the inlet velocity also shows an increase in the methanol production due to an increased interface area, enhancing mass transfer between the gas and liquid phase.

CO₂ might also be reduced to multicarbon products (C₂, C₃). Although their economic value far surpasses C₁ products, the substantial drawback in their production is a comparatively low efficiency/yield. While outside of scope for this work, a recent review by Du et al.¹⁸⁷ discusses recent progress in the field of photocatalytic and electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to hydrocarbons. Cu-based catalysts are most often used, but recently MoS₂ and metallic Pd with boron doping were also probed.

Multi-scale models are far and few between. The reasons, although not clearly stated, most likely lie in the complexity of a photocatalytic reaction. While the properties of photocatalysts and their interaction with reactants can be calculated with great accuracy, most studies forego the treatment of excited states and solvent effects due to the computational cost involved. This means that the mechanism is only approximately known. The barriers are essentially those of thermocatalytic reduction, making coupling of first-principle calculations with microkinetic models and kMC simulations moot. A successful coupling of DFT with kMC^{188,189} and microkinetics^{190,191} has already been observed in other fields, whereas photocatalytic CO₂ reduction remains largely underutilized. The next rung on the multi-scale ladder, a successful coupling of kMC and microkinetics with CFD, has also been performed^{181,192}. An overarching model, encompassing all levels, remains to be realised.

8 Conclusion

Photocatalysis is increasingly becoming an important alternative for reducing CO₂ emissions. While harbouring the potential for a cheaper and environmentally friendlier way of converting CO₂ than the traditional catalytic approaches, it has yet to manifest its full potential. While experimental data are abundant, the theoretical investigations remain limited, mostly focusing on describing one material or used supplementarily to experimental results. Broad screening campaigns, comparative analyses or exhaustive mechanism treatments are lacking.

Nonetheless, in recent years theoretical studies have begun to take off. The recent advances in the available computational power have caused the number of purely theoretical studies to surge. Some studies are contrasted with experiments, especially in terms of electronic properties such as CB, VB, band gap, charge transfer, and charge separation calculations. In this review, we focused on the theoretical description of the CO₂ photoreduction and evaluated the current methodology and trends.

Despite a plethora of the theoretical methods available, density functional theory calculations in a plane-wave approach are most commonly used. GGA approaches are most commonly used for initial calculations, but are being increasingly supplemented with hybrid functionals (such as HSE06 or PBE0), often as single-point calculations. When GGA (most often PBE) is used, a van der Waals correction by Grimme (D2 or D3) are almost universally applied, while the less popular Tkatchenko and Scheffler method also occasionally pops up. When hybrid functional calculations are not desired due to computational cost, the DFT+U approach is used as a surrogate. This method, albeit no more computationally expensive as GGA, suffers from the inherent untransferability of the U parameter, which has to be set for every system, usually by fitting to experimental data. PBE0 and HSE06 are technically not truly *ab initio*, as the mixing parameter was chosen arbitrarily (by fitting), yet have proved to be a good choice for periodic insulating systems (such as TiO₂). Due to its limitations, B3LYP

is more suitable for molecular systems, whereas PBE0 and HSE06 are commonly employed for periodic structures.

Regarding kinetic modelling and macro-scale simulations of photocatalysis, this field is still in its infancy and mostly applied to the thermocatalytic CO₂ reduction due to its simpler nature compared to the photocatalytic reduction. Simplifications have to be made to perform multi-scale modelling. At the electronic level, solvent effects and excited states are amongst the more important aspects, yet most studies ignore them completely. Coupling these results with kMC or microkinetics is a starting point for multiscale models and can subsequently be used as boundary conditions in CFD simulations. There have been studies such as that of Braham et al.¹⁸³ that coupled kMC with CFD for photocatalytic system, where the kMC input was derived from first-principles calculations. However, such studies are rarely applied to realistic photocatalytic systems.

In most cases, TiO₂ and g-C₃N₄ stand out as the catalysts of choice. As they are photocatalytically active on their own, their modifications are a promising approach to utilizing them in CO₂ reduction. While photocatalysts with wide band gaps absorb UV light, it is desirable to identify those that can utilize lower frequencies, as well (visible spectrum). This can be achieved with doping, defects (such as oxygen vacancies), cocatalysts or by employing the Z-scheme type. Nevertheless, the effect of these modifications has to be critically evaluated, as some might act as recombination centres, thus hindering the photocatalytic activity, while others have a positive effect.

Suitable photocatalysts should activate the CO₂ molecule, which is rather inert. Upon adsorption, the C-O bond is elongated and the molecule is bent, as CO₂⁻ is formed. Defects and cocatalysts generally improve the activation of the molecule and act as electron sinks. Another important aspect of the catalyst is the exposed surface, as different surfaces exhibit different affinities towards CO₂ and consequently also the intermediates and products. Theoretical studies can screen and thus predict the most suitable surfaces for a desired pathway, therefore combining theoretical results with surface engineering is a promising new field.

The most common products of CO₂ photoreduction are CO, methanol and methane, although formaldehyde, formic acid and hydrocarbons can also form. Simulations show that most suitable photocatalysts exhibit low band-gaps (visible light spectrum absorption), high charge transfer and good charge separations. While pristine catalysts, e.g. TiO₂ and g-C₃N₄, have good properties, they also possess deficiencies such as a high band-gap and a high recombination rate for TiO₂ and g-C₃N₄ respectively. To improve on them one can resort to defects integration (doping/oxygen vacancies), cocatalysts (electron traps) or a synergistic system of combining 2 catalysts as in the Z-scheme catalyst. The current trends seem to follow these guidelines, doping the studied material, depositing one or several co-catalysts (usually (noble) metals), oxygen vacancies incorporation or any possible combination, while some investigations are starting to shift their focus towards identification of novel photocatalysts (e.g. B₄C₃).

It is difficult to computationally predict the reaction products as one has to investigate all possible reaction pathways. Nonetheless, theoretical insights can provide important clues and often achieve good agreement with experiments. Methane and methanol are the most prominent products, with a possibility of CO and HCOOH depending on the modifications. While pristine g-C₃N₄ most likely favours methanol and methane production, modifications such as codoping can shift that selectivity towards methane via the carbene pathway. Metal cocatalysts mostly prefer the formation of methane, methanol or formaldehyde. Most reactions proceed via HCOOH, while the carbene pathway yields methane. Different modifications can also shift CBM/VBM to the formation of a certain product, while doping and cocatalysts can introduce midgap states. This can either benefit the photocatalysis with a better charge separation or harm it as recombination centres.

Although the theoretical methods for describing the interaction of photons with matter as applied in photocatalysis are getting mature, there is still room for improvement. More costly methods are still not used on larger systems due to their computational cost. Most theoretical work is done without accounting for excited states and solvent effects, while some investigations are starting to take them

into account. Despite their known shortcomings, GGA pseudopotentials with simple van der Waals corrections are the predominant approach. In the future, larger screening campaigns will allow for a systematic approach towards photocatalyst improvement and discovery. Moreover, the integration of electronic structure calculations into higher scale simulations (kinetics, computational fluid dynamics *etc.*) will result in multiscale models, encompassing all reaction scales from the atom to macroscopic level.

9 Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the Slovenian Research Agency for funding (Core Grant P2-0152 and Grant N2-0135). Ž. K. appreciates the financial support from the European Commission through a Horizon 2020 Project (ReaxPro, Grant N. 814416). M. H. also acknowledges the Slovenian Research Agency for Infrastructure Grant I0-0039.

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